

Palladium in Organic Synthesis. Part-V. Palladium-catalysed Insertion of Chloroarenes to the Olefins using Cobalt as Co-catalyst

JAYATI MITRA and ALOK KUMAR MITRA*

Department of Chemistry, University College of Science, Calcutta-700 009

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Palladium-catalysed Heck arylation and vinylation to the olefins are important reactions in organic syntheses¹. Generally aromatic bromides and iodides couple to the activated olefins in the presence of palladium(0). The reaction is general for a wide range of substituents on aromatic halides as well as on olefins; as a result, the Heck reaction has been exploited extensively in the synthesis of natural products². Recently this reaction is being utilised in asymmetric synthesis using chiral phosphines³. One of the limitations of the Heck reaction is its failure with aromatic chloro compounds, though for the vinyl chloride⁴ the reaction takes place smoothly. Palladium-catalysed coupling of bromobenzene to ethyl acrylate under Heck reaction condition furnishes ethyl cinnamate in 78% yield⁵, whereas under identical condition using chlorobenzene instead of bromobenzene, gives ethyl cinnamate in very poor yield to the extent of 4%⁶.

In our continued efforts for exploiting palladium in organic synthesis⁷, we herein report a novel method for the insertion of aromatic chloro compounds to olefins in moderate yield, in the presence of a catalytic amount of palladium(0) and cobalt salt as a co-catalyst. Thus inexpensive chloroarenes could couple to olefins under this modified method. By this method chloroarenes, viz. chlorobenzene (1), 2-nitrochlorobenzene (2) couple to the ac-

furnish cinnamic acid (5) and ethyl cinnamate (6) in 42 and 35% yield respectively. Similarly, 2-nitrochlorobenzene (2) couples with acrylic acid (3) to give 3-(2-nitrophenyl)acrylic acid (7) in 25% yield. The structures of the products have been determined by their ir and nmr spectrometric data and also by comparison with the other physical data of the known compounds.

The blank experiment with chlorobenzene (1) and acrylic acid (3) was also carried out in the presence of all the ingredients except cobalt bromide; in this case the coupled product was obtained in very poor yield of nearly 6%. So addition of cobalt bromide remarkably enhances the reactivity of chloroarenes towards insertion to olefins. To our knowledge this is the first report of utilisation of palladium-cobalt catalytic system in the Heck insertion reaction. Further work with chloroarenes having different substituents and olefins with different activating groups and a variety of phosphines under different reaction conditions to increase the yield is now in progress. It is interesting to observe that during this reaction with the compound containing ester group, a coupled product is also obtained in which cleavage of ester group has occurred. Investigation for the reason of this peculiar result is at present being pursued in our laboratory. However, the promotion of Heck reaction of chloroarenes with alkenes is known with other transition metal salts (nickel(II) bromide) in the presence of sodium iodide⁹.

Experimental

Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 782 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Bruker AM-300 spectrometer (300 MHz) with tetramethylsilane as internal standard. Silica gel (B.D.H., 60-120 mesh) was used for column chromatography.

Cinnamic acid (5): A mixture of chlorobenzene (0.55 g, 5 mmol), cobalt bromide (0.22 g, 1 mmol) and sodium iodide (0.80 g, 5.5 mmol) in DMF (1 ml) was heated at 130° in argon atmosphere for 4 h. The mixture was then cooled to room temperature and acrylic acid (0.40 g, 5.5 mmol), Pd₂(dba)₃ (0.02 g, 0.025 mmol), triphenylphosphine (0.5 g, 2 mmol) and triethylamine (4 ml) were added and the resulting mixture was again plunged with argon and heated at 130° for 20 h. The blue coloured product was poured into cold water and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was extracted with aqueous sodium bicarbonate

Scheme 1

tivated olefins, viz. acrylic acid (3), ethyl acrylate (4) in the presence of a catalytic amount of tris(dibenzylideneacetone)dipalladium(0) [Pd₂(dba)₃]⁸, cobalt(II) bromide, triphenylphosphine, sodium iodide, triethylamine, when heated in DMF at 130° in argon atmosphere for 20 h (Scheme 1). Thus chlorobenzene (1) couples to acrylic acid (3) and ethyl acrylate (4) separately under this condition to

and the latter on acidification furnished a white solid (5: 0.3 g), 135° (hot water); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 100–2 500, 1 700, 1 640, 1 590, 1 460, 1 430, 770, 710 cm^{-1} . The ir spectra of 5 is superimposable with that of authentic sample of cinnamic acid.

Ethyl cinnamate (6) : The reaction procedure was identical to the preceding procedure with chlorobenzene (0.55 g, 5 mmol) and ethyl acrylate (0.55 g, 5.5 mmol). After the reaction was over, the crude product was cooled, treated with ice-cold water and acidified with dilute HCl and extracted with ether. The residue after removal of solvent was subjected to the column chromatography over silica gel. Ethyl acetate-petroleum ether (1 : 10) eluent furnished ethyl cinnamate (6, 0.3 g) as a colourless liquid : $\nu_{\max}$ (neat) 3 000–2 900, 1 700, 1 630, 1 500, 1 450, 760, 700 cm^{-1} ; δ 1.27 (3H, t, J 7.1 Hz, CH_3), 4.20 (2H, q, J 7.1 Hz, CH_2), 6.37 (1H, d, J 16.1 Hz, $\text{C}_2\text{-H}$), 7.29–7.47 (5H, m, ArH), 7.62 (1H, d, J 16.1 Hz, $\text{C}_3\text{-H}$).

3-(2-Nitrophenyl)acrylic acid (7) : After the reaction with 2-chloronitrobenzene (0.78 g, 5 mmol) and acrylic acid (0.4 g, 5.5 mmol) under identical condition described previously, the black gummy mass was treated with ice-cold water and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was then extracted with excess of saturated aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution, acidified with dilute HCl and extracted into chloroform. The crude product obtained upon removal of solvent was crystallised, m.p. 120° (ether-petroleum ether) to furnish 7 (0.23 g); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 400, 3 300–2 500, 1 700, 1 635, 1 600, 1 580, 1 510, 800, 740 cm^{-1} ; δ 6.38 (1H, d, J 16 Hz, $\text{C}_2\text{-H}$), 7.33–7.50 (4H, m, ArH), 7.72 (1H, d, J 16 Hz, $\text{C}_3\text{-H}$).

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References

1. R. F. HECK, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1979, **12**, 146; *Org. React.*, 1982, **27**.
2. L. S. HEGEDUS, M. R. SESTRICK, E. T. MICHAELSON and P. J. HARRINGTON, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1989, **54**, 4141; G. DYKER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1993, **58**, 234; V. H. RAWAL and C. MICHOU. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1993, **58**, 5583; R. C. LAROCK, E. K. YUM and H. YANG. *Tetrahedron*, 1994, **50**, 305; T. SAKAMOTO, Y. KONDO, K. MASUMOTO and H. YAMANAKA, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1994, 235; S. LASCHAT, F. NARJES and L. E. OVERMAN, *Tetrahedron*, 1994, **50**, 347; T. JEFFERY, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1994, **35**, 3051; A. DE MEIJERE and F. E. MEYER, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1994, **33**, 2379.
3. Y. SATO, S. NUKUI, M. SODEBOKA and M. SHIBASAKI. *Tetrahedron*, 1994, **50**, 371; Y. KOGA, M. SODEBOKA and M. SHIBASAKI, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1994, **35**, 1227.
4. J. S. YADAV, P. K. DESHPANDE and G. V. M. SHARMA. *Tetrahedron*, 1992, **48**, 4465.
5. B. A. PATEL, C. B. ZIEGLER, N. A. CORTESE, J. E. PLAÉVYAK, T. C. ZEBOVITZ, M. TERPKO and R. F. HECK, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1977, **42**, 3903
6. M. JULIA and M. DUTEL, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Fr.*, 1973, 2790; A. J. SPENCER, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1984, **270**, 115.
7. J. MITRA and A. K. MITRA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1992, **31**, 613, 693; 1994, **33**, 276; "Abstract, Tenth International Conference on Organic Synthesis", Bangalore, 1994, p. 213.
8. T. UKAI, H. KANAZURA, Y. ISHII, J. J. BONNETT and J. A. IBERS, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1974, **65**, 253.
9. J. J. BOZELL and C. E. VOGT, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **110**, 2655.